

Nonsense and Transformative Experience

From Breaking Meaning to Making Meaning

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Abstract

Transformative experiences are intellectually and emotionally cohesive experiences that shift how people view the world. For designers, developing these experiences can prove difficult. In this work, I argue that *nonsense* can provide an engaging route to transformations.

Usually understood as “meaningless” acts, nonsense may seem like an enemy to understanding. On the contrary, I argue that nonsense can aid people in the meaning-making process. When nonsense is resolved—that is, when a user reorganizes information that has been disorganized—a change in cognition occurs. This change is not passive: it is active emotional and intellectual learning, which relates directly to the imperative of designing for transformative experiences.

While both defying expectations and working within them, nonsense can pleasantly disrupt the status quo and inspire real change in people. Nonsense—through the organization, disorganization, and reorganization of information that it necessitates—relies on the disruption of expectation as its primary route to transformative experience.

In a cross-disciplinary overview of the cognitive roots of nonsense and its manifestations in the fine arts and linguistics, I explore how nonsense can be used as a powerful rhetorical device. From this exploration, I have developed a set of heuristics for designers who want to create the framework for transformative experiences.

Key Words: design, nonsense, emotion, rhetoric, dissonance.

Introduction: The Heuristics of Nonsense

If common sense is “an organization of the world, as a model of order, integrity, and coherence accomplished in social life” [1] then nonsense would seem to disorganize this structure. Nonsense is the variation of a pattern, a hiccup in reality, a mismatch between what is perceived and what is believed. Usually berated, nonsense can actually help people to reorganize complex information, thereby creating fresh models of understanding and coherence.

An in-depth exploration of nonsense in design has not yet been undertaken, yet the cognitive and emotional effects of nonsense have the utmost relevance to the types of experiences that designers work to create. Nonsense spurs people to challenge their pre-conceived assumptions. It shows people the world from a topsy-turvy perspective, causing them to link information in a new way—like a child swinging upside-down from monkey bars seeing an unexplored corner of the playground. Unlike the child’s accidental exploration, however, nonsense can be carefully facilitated. *Designers* can use nonsense as a powerful rhetorical tool to create and guide people through cohesive and transformative experiences.

1. Rhetoric and Organization

Design—like rhetoric—is an activity of persuasion, an attempt to cause a shift in thinking and a change in action [2]. A fundamental problem designers have in creating this shift is finding a way to disrupt a person’s long held pattern of belief and make him or her stop, think, and feel his or her way through information. This can be especially challenging for a designer when that information either contradicts current assumptions or poses some kind of threat to the “status quo.” A transformative experience brought about by nonsense can invite exactly this effect by helping a person to reorganize information that has been thoughtfully disorganized by a designer. This reorganization is key to developing an altered intellectual and emotional understanding, because it gives added weight to new ideas.

Reorganizing nonsense requires a person to abandon previous models of understanding and undergo the rebuilding of a new framework of information. Nonsense breaks down the natural resistance to new information because it does not forcefully impose the new idea, but rather introduces it in a less threatening sequence. For example, the riddled exchange between Hamlet and a gravedigger-clown, Hamlet must constantly adapt to the gravedigger’s lyrical nonsense, building up to the moment of full understanding that the grave is for his beloved Ophelia:

HAMLET What man dost thou dig it for?

GRAVEDIGGER For no man, sir.

HAMLET What woman, then?

GRAVEDIGGER For none, neither.

HAMLET Who is to be buried in’t?

GRAVEDIGGER One that was a woman, sir;
but, rest her soul, she’s dead. [3]

At first, Hamlet assumes the death of a stranger. In this moment, only his mind is engaged. The subsequent conversation sparks Hamlet's emotions as the finality of death hits him. This example illustrates a meaningful experience for Hamlet where mind, then heart are sequentially, but cohesively engaged.

As Shakespeare's work suggests, nonsense can be an extremely effective rhetorical device that encourages the struggle to develop an emotionally and intellectually cohesive perspective, capable of embracing a challenging idea—and perhaps unparalleled. Nonsense begins to answer a challenge set forth by design thinkers to design for experiences [4, 5] as a way to help people learn and grow. Hamlet's unfolding of information is one way to create intellectually and emotionally cohesive experiences that can lead to fundamental changes in how people view the world. This paper will show how that approach, along with others, allows the confusion that exists in the realm of nonsense to be pulled back into the real world as newly-linked information.

Heuristic 1

Nonsense relies on disorganization.

2. Dissonance and Action

Nonsense is an effective way to present a mismatch between what is perceived and what is believed. Social psychologists call the effects of this kind of mismatch *cognitive dissonance*. When encountering dissonance, the mind races in an attempt to resolve contradictory ideas and doesn't rest until the inconsistency has been justified.

When information inconsistent with cognitions that guide action is encountered, negative emotion (dissonance) is aroused because the dissonant information has the potential to interfere with effective and unconflicted action... Thus, negative emotion works much like pain in that it provides the information and motivation that prompts the person to engage in cognitive action aimed at resolving the discrepancy. [9]

Human behavior is guided by personal sets of beliefs and values perceived as meaningful truth—such as understanding that gravity governs physical objects. When something in the environment appears to violate this truth (e.g. a magic trick that appears to violate the laws of gravity), dissonance occurs and a person strives to make sense of the world again. He or she either works to maintain the status quo, or works to give enough weight to the new idea, creating a new set of beliefs that eliminate the conflict. As the person puts more weight on these new ideas, the “pain” of dissonance is overcome and the threat recedes.

For example, an estranged father is confronted with information that children with absent fathers face a far higher risk of school dropout and drug abuse. This information is dissonant with the knowledge that he has not made an effort to connect with his children for many months. He can eliminate the dissonance by changing his behavior and scheduling time to play with his children—or he could eliminate the dissonant idea by discounting the statistics as skewed or bogus. He could also justify his absence by thinking that his kids are better off without him.

It is important for designers to understand this kind of behavior in order to help people take in information they would otherwise be averse to. For example, a designer could typeset a beautiful and accurate brochure with all the statistics about parenting mentioned above, but it will still be ignored by the estranged father, who is cognitively resistant to such information. Using *nonsense* to add weight to certain cognitions might be the way to help people engage in different kinds of thinking and behavior.

Designers trained in simplicity and usability might dismiss the idea of adding a layer of complexity to their work, but nonsense and the dissonance effects that it creates flourish in the fine arts and prove to be powerful ways of helping people take in new ideas.

A recent study tested the result of a threat to a person's framework of meaning [10]. Meaning, defined in the study as "a set of expected associations that are derived from, and impose order upon, one's experiences" [11], was threatened for some participants by reading a nonsensical short story by Franz Kafka. This group, and a control group that read a straightforward short story, subsequently performed a pattern-recognition test. Reading the absurd story provoked "motivations to perceive unrelated patterns in the environment, and similarly enhance[d] the ability to learn unrelated patterns that are present" [12]. In this case, nonsense—and the threat it poses to perceived truth—elicited dissonance effects that led to creative thinking and new behaviors, suggesting that a breakdown in meaning can lead to a transformation in cognition and, importantly, new kinds of action.

Heuristic 2

**Nonsense can be employed without resolution
as a first step toward more creative thinking.**

3. Contradiction and Cognition

A contradiction of meaning has been studied in the context of visual and verbal modalities of communication [13]. When image and text collaborate, they can "challenge, contradict, or clarify the ordinary, or associative, meaning of isolated modalities [14]." The cover of the December 1940 issue of *Direction Magazine* is given as an example of a contradiction of the default meanings of an image and text (see Figure 1). As the example shows, the iconic illustration by Paul Rand is that of a present with a cheery handwritten tag. But, in place of ribbon, the package is wrapped with barbed wire.

Figure.1 Paul Rand, *Direction* cover, Dec. 1940.
Source: Susan Hagan, Visual/Verbal Collaboration in Print,
Written Communication, Jan. 07.

“Merry Christmas,” held captive in a barbed-wire package, communicates a horrific irony manifested in a presentation of contradictions, contradictions that challenge the idea of merriment in the face of the tragedies of World War II. [15]

This breakdown in the ordinary meanings of objects and words is a striking embodiment of cognitive dissonance, demonstrating its possible rhetorical power to “encourage reflection, broaden motivation, and improve learning outside of the audience’s stated goals [16].”

Visual/verbal contradiction focuses on how the ambiguous meanings of words (such as “Merry Christmas”) and objects (like the barbed wire) allow an audience to accept new meanings created by new pairings. *Nonsense* engages in a level of disorganization and unexpectedness that allows people to more thoroughly examine their preconceived notions. This deep dive into questioning of expectations could bring about real transformative thinking.

Heuristic 3

**Nonsense is not visual/verbal contradiction,
it involves a deeper questioning of expectations.**

4. Structure and Resolution

As it manifests as cognitive dissonance, carefully designed nonsense can help people shift their frameworks of meaning and gain different perspectives, create new ideas, or even make something known, new again. Nonsense has been used to create these effects for hundreds of years in the fields of linguistics and drama [17]. By studying how nonsense is used and perceived in these fields, designers can further learn to use nonsense effectively to design for transformative experiences.

Without structure, language cannot be meaningful. Though it may not seem like it on the surface, nonsense verse is highly structured and governed by rules. Consider Lewis Carroll’s Jabberwocky:

’Twas brillig, and the slithy toves
Did gyre and gimble in the wabe:
All mimsy were the borogoves,
And the mome raths outgrabe. [18]

It is grammatically correct, yet semantically confusing. It follows just enough of the rules of language that a reader can reorganize the gibberish to make meaning from it. The result is a uniquely personal and emotional ownership and intellectual understanding that can only be created by the reorganization of information necessitated by nonsense. People who put time into Jabberwocky come away with varying levels of understanding and delight [19].

Figure.2 Source: Lewis Caroll, *Through the Looking-Glass and What Alice Found There*, 1871.

A similar pattern holds true for the Icelandic post-rock band, Sigur Rós. Lead singer Jónsi Birgisson sings in a made-up language that lacks grammar, but gains meaning from sounds and rhythm—much like scat. Semantically and grammatically, the songs are gibberish—but the made-up language follows a strict law of emotion and sound that makes the music meaningful and enjoyable to listeners.

As these examples show, structure and organization on the part of the emitter is the line that keeps nonsense from slipping into pointless absurdity. Nonsense is not complete disorder, it means something to the writer that can be reorganized by the receiver. Lewis Carroll and Jónsi Birgisson understand the meaning of their verse, which is what allowed them to disorganize the meaning into nonsense so that their audiences can reorganize the information and make new meaning. Nonsense verse—like other forms of nonsense—requires extra effort on the part of the receiver. Readers have to go through the process of creating a new framework of meaning. This additional demand on the user may seem contrary to a human-centered view of design. For example, reading Jabberwocky may require extra time and effort before it can reveal meaning to the reader. But, despite its veneer of gibberish, Jabberwocky has enraptured readers for over a century. This personal reorganization along both cognitive and emotional avenues points to a way that designers can begin to think about an approach to nonsense.

Heuristic 4

Fit nonsense into a known structure; nonsense must involve a careful balance of the known and the unknown.

5. Nonsense and Resolution

Conversely, nonsense can be frustrating when it doesn't resolve into meaning or understanding. Pushing on a door when you should pull is an example of disruption with no aesthetic outcome. Certainly, there are right and wrong times to wield the dissonance effects of nonsense. In the case of nonsense verse, the ubiquity and sustained popularity of nursery rhymes is a telling sign that the discomfort of confusion is outweighed by the delight derived “from the separation of word and meaning” [20]. When nonsense comes to a resolution, the result is an experience that engages emotion and intellect—delighting the user on an aesthetic plane:

Puns, paradoxes, and all such self-conscious displays of simultaneously probable and improbable coincidence are like circus acts and sideshow menageries. Displayed as oddities to the minds that are audience to them, they reinforce our confidence in the norm with which they contrast and from which they are so efficiently isolated. The same is true of magician's tricks [21].

By at once defying expectations and working within them, nonsense can pleasantly disrupt the status quo and create transformative experiences. By coming to an aesthetic resolution, nonsense maintains its relevance and delightfulness.

Heuristic 5

Nonsense must be resolved in an aesthetic way.

6. Redundant Cues

I believe that nonsense is capable of not only transforming *cognition* but also of changing *action* in the real world. Audiences must be primed for such changes, however. Careful structuring to ensure resolution of nonsense is essential to designing effective experiences for people.

In *Art as Experience*, John Dewey writes a chapter about the nature of experience [22]. What he calls an “esthetic” experience aligns with the “transformative” experience I argue for here. Dewey’s esthetic experience unites the emotional and intellectual to come to a holistic understanding—just the kind of experiences designers strive to create. By again stepping across disciplines, we can see that *theater* has been creating such holistic experiences for audiences for thousands of years. The decisions that a director makes with lighting, sets, costumes, language, program notes, and the theater space itself, all add up to a calculated facilitation of an experience for the audience. Those decisions across multiple interests result in redundant cues that give additional weight to the new idea.

An actress comes screaming onto a stage, wearing a red dress, followed by a red spotlight. There is screeching music playing, and pyrotechnics are set off in the wings. Some redundancy is required when communicating a message, but, as a skilled director knows, restraint must be practiced [23]. Just as a typographer would not normally bold, italicize, and underline 24-point type, a designer who is designing for experience must choose one or two modes of emphasis to get the point across. However, redundancy is necessary in any kind of communication [24] and can be especially effective when employing nonsense when designing for experience.

For example, a recent Pittsburgh Irish and Classical Theater adaptation of *Crime and Punishment* featured a sparsely dressed stage. One of the four wooden set pieces was a free-standing door—which stood about two feet shorter than a normal door, causing the actors to duck when they “entered” the main character’s room. This break in pattern of what the audience would normally consider to be a door brings attention to that set piece, which turns out to have special significance. The impoverished protagonist, Rodion, lives in a squalid one-room apartment under the stairs, with a ceiling so low it doesn’t allow him to stand up straight. This subtle interplay of set and dialogue shapes the audience’s emotional and intellectual experience of the play with just enough “nonsense” (the misshapen door) and “structure” (the redundancy when the character describes the condition of his living quarters). Rodion is physically, emotionally, and mentally confined, and the nonsense of the door acts as a metaphor that disrupts the status quo so that a deeper understanding can be possible.

While in theater, sequence is more obvious, designers have default sequence at their command because of the structure and function of the human eye. While the sequence in the play allowed a clear time difference between the door and the explanation for this door, the function of vision means that the audience must look in sequence, taking in one thing before resolving it with another.

Heuristic 6

Use redundant cues sparingly and with attention to sequence to clarify nonsense.

Summary

As we see in linguistics and theatre, when using nonsense to design for transformative experiences, the triumvirate of organization, disorganization, and reorganization is key. It is also essential to understand the cognitive effects that come to play when a person encounters nonsense. The dissonant ideas brought up by nonsense can only be resolved when a person gives more weight to one idea over the other. Designers, with the right knowledge, can nudge people toward this cognitive leap towards a transformative experience.

The psychology of nonsense, its importance in creativity, and its implementation in linguistics and theater begs to be synthesized into a set of heuristics for designers to use when designing for transformative experiences. These heuristics include:

1. Rhetoric and Organization

Nonsense relies on disorganization, which can emerge from several sources [25]. The following four categories of representation can serve as guidelines when a designer must thoughtfully disorganize information so that it can be reorganized and interpreted into a meaningful message.

Reverse/Invert Reversals and inversions of known assumptions, such as contradiction and opposition, can lead to disorganization. Example: The gravedigger turns Hamlet's words around on him, saying that the grave belongs to no man or woman, but "one that was a woman."

Reduce/Expand Playing with boundaries and infinity, such as in acts of exaggeration, magnification, or understatement, can help people see information from new perspectives. Example: The too-short door in the Pittsburgh Irish and Classical Theater production of Crime and Punishment used reduction to emphasize the diminutive living quarters of the protagonist.

Layer/Combine The use of simultaneity, such as in superimposition, amalgamation, portmanteau, or chimera, can lead to thoughtful disorganization. Example: The language used in Lewis Carroll's Jabberwocky and the Jabberwocky itself are examples of simultaneity: amalgamations of phonemes, jaws, and claws.

Change/Rearrange By arranging and rearranging language or objects, people can begin to create new frames of reference. For example, juxtaposition, pun, duplication, repetition, and alliteration all rely upon creative arrangement and rearrangement. Example: The rhythm and repetition in the gibberish lyrics of Sigur Rós are a modern incarnation of ages-old nursery rhymes (such as Hey Diddle Diddle and Hickory Dickory Dock).

2. Dissonance and Action

Nonsense can be employed without resolution as first step toward more creative thinking. However, designers should be aware that unresolved nonsense has the danger of becoming frustrating or hum-drum rather than a pleasurable and engaging.

3. Contradiction and Cognition

Nonsense is not visual/verbal contradiction—it involves a deeper questioning of expectations. Beyond the surprise created by ambiguity in meaning of words and objects, nonsense can help people create entirely new meanings that are totally different than prior beliefs.

4. Structure and Resolution

Nonsense must involve a careful balance of the known and the unknown. Careful structuring of nonsense within a familiar framework can help ease people into the experience of changing the way they think.

5. Nonsense and Resolution

Nonsense must be resolved in an aesthetic way. Only nonsense that can be reorganized back into meaningful information can lead to transformative experiences. Without resolution, the experience remains disorganized and unaesthetic.

6. Redundant Cues

Use redundant cues sparingly and with attention to sequence to clarify nonsense. The unfolding of experience can help lead to real transformation in the way people think and act.

Conclusion

When we encounter a disruption in the normal activities of our lives (for example, a kangaroo bounding through downtown Pittsburgh) our brains goes into overdrive, endeavoring to make sense of the situation and to find a recognizable pattern. Freud called these moments where the world as we know it kind of break down as “the uncanny”—something unfamiliar and uncertain, “something which ought to have remained hidden but has come to light” [26].

Cognitive dissonance—the flood of emotion and intellectual stimulation that accompanies the unexpected and seemingly illogical moments in life—is a powerful paradigm of human psychology. People strive to create meaning in their lives, and designers can tap into this powerful rhetorical opportunity through the use of nonsense that disorganizes in order to create a fresh model of meaning and coherence. Nonsense—and the organization, disorganization, and reorganization that it requires—can disrupt expectations to create transformative experiences.

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